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2 **Dosage effect of Copy Number Variation in Epilepsy and ten regions of the**
3 **human brain**
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8 **Tisham De^{1,2,3*}, Lachlan Coin^{3,4,§}, Michael R Johnson^{5,§}**

- 9 1. **Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, School of Public Health, Imperial**
10 **College, London, UK**
11 2. **Department of Genomics of Common Diseases, Imperial College London, UK**
12 3. **Department of Infectious Diseases, Imperial College London, UK**
13 4. **Department of Microbiology and Immunology, University of Melbourne at The**
14 **Peter Doherty, Institute for Infection and Immunity, Melbourne, Australia**
15 5. **Department of Brain Sciences, Imperial College London, UK**
16

17 * Email: tisham.de08@imperial.ac.uk or de.tisham@gmail.com

18 § Joint senior authors
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20

21 **Abstract**
22

23 Epilepsy and seizures are one of the most common neurological conditions which often manifest
24 with complex symptoms. Several studies including large scale GWAS and exome studies have
25 reported a comprehensive catalog of genes related to Epilepsy. Similarly, there exists several
26 successful studies elucidating the role of SNP QTLs in the normal human brain. Here, as one of
27 few studies in current literature we have explored and reported the dosage effect of small to
28 intermediate length CNVs in two Epilepsy cohorts characterized for phenotypes such as seizure
29 counts, seizure frequency and remission to anti-epilepsy drugs. In addition, we have performed
30 comprehensive CNV QTL analysis in ten regions of the human brain (normal) from the UKBEC
31 study. We leveraged all analyses to decipher new genes for Epilepsy phenotypes such as seizure
32 frequency and further uncovered genetic controls of neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine
33 and signaling molecules like GPCRs. Importantly we observed and have reported clustering of

34 CNV QTL signals in specific regions of the genome such as the chromosome 1p36 proband
35 containing the GNB1 gene or the chromosome 9q22 proband containing NANS. This observed
36 phenomenon of clustering of association signals was further corroborated by our non-negative
37 matrix factorization (NMF) analysis of UKBEC gene expression data. To conclude our results here
38 successfully describe in detail the dosage effect of CNVs for Epilepsy seizures and further
39 elucidates its role in the genomic architecture of gene expression in various regions of the human
40 brain.

41

42 **Introduction**

43 Epilepsy is a common neurological disease affecting around 1% of the population worldwide.
44 Anti-epileptic drugs in general work well for 60% of Epilepsy patients who successfully achieve
45 seizure control with current medication within a year or two, however for around one third or 20-
46 30% patients, the latest anti-epilepsy drugs (25 licensed drugs worldwide^{1,2}) do not work well and
47 these patients continue to have regular seizures^{3,4}. Further it has been observed that resistance to
48 one anti-epileptic drug correlates well with resistance to all other drugs. Current anti-epileptic
49 medication is not prescribed for vulnerable groups such as pregnant women. One off seizure are
50 quite common in young children and adults but are usually termed benign. For some refractory
51 groups of Epilepsy patients who do not respond to standard medication a brain surgery is required
52 to control seizures^{5,6}. In these cases, first an exploratory surgery is required to identify regions of
53 the brain where seizures originated (which can be almost anywhere in the brain) and then a second
54 surgery is needed to remove these regions. In some rare cases of Epilepsy known as Lennox-
55 gastaut syndromes, which often originates in the occipital lobe of the brain, a child may have
56 numerous seizures a day. As a part of the CADET trial (Children's Adaptive Deep brain

57 stimulation for Epilepsy Trial), United Kingdom's first patient, a child with Lennox-gastaut
58 syndrome with mutations in the SCN1B gene¹, was successfully implanted with a device in the
59 brain to control seizures through electric pulses. Chromodomain-helicase-DNA-binding protein 2
60 or the CHD2 gene is another candidate gene for this syndrome⁷.

61
62 However, little is known about the biology of brain seizures, the regions where it originates and
63 the causal mechanisms behind it. Thus, the genetic basis of seizures remains an open question in
64 neurology. Here we present comprehensive copy number variation (CNV) analysis for Epilepsy
65 phenotypes including seizure counts, seizure frequency and 12-month remission to anti-epileptic
66 drugs in two cohorts, denoted as SANAD and Australian cohort⁴. In addition we have also analysed
67 and reported here CNV-gene expression signatures (CNV eQTLs) in ten regions of the normal
68 human brain from the UKBEC⁸ and NABEC⁹⁻¹¹ studies. We leveraged all analyses to decipher
69 new gene clusters and loci for neurobiology of seizures and report the phenomenon of reciprocal
70 CNV dosage in genes related to neurotransmitters and GPCR mediated signal transduction in
71 different regions of the human brain.

72

73 **Results**

74 **CNV analysis in Epilepsy cohorts**

75 In our main discovery cohort SANAD, the top hit for CNV genotypes was GNB1 for the phenotype
76 total number of seizures (chr1:1745726, p-value=2.89e-168, MAF=1.1%) and seizure frequency
77 (chr1:1745726, p-value=2.82e-95) (**Figure 1, Supplementary table 1a**). In addition, GNB1 also
78 replicated as the top hit in the joint model (chr1:1745726, p-value=6.3e-202) and joint model with

¹ <https://www.gosh.nhs.uk/news/first-uk-trial-of-deep-brain-stimulation-for-children-with-epilepsy-begins-at-gosh/>

79 variable selection using CNV genotypes (chr1:1745726, p-value=2.27e-207) (**Supplementary**
80 **table 1a**). In the clinvar database annotations for GNB1 we observed that pathogenic CNVs were
81 more numerous than pathogenic SNVs thus adding more weight to our CNV results
82 (**Supplementary table 2**). In Log R Ratio (LRR) based models the strongest signal was found
83 within *growth hormone receptor gene* (GHR) (chr5:42569642, p-value < 6e-128)
84 (**Supplementary table 1a**). In SANAD the top gene for drug-response was TRAPPC9
85 (chr8:140765991, p-value=1.7e-05, LRR univariate model, **Supplementary table 1a**). TRAPPC9
86 is used for clinical diagnosis of a rare neuro-endocrine disease *Intellectual disability-obesity-brain*
87 *malformations-facial dysmorphism syndrome*¹² (Malacards.org).

88 We further noticed that in SANAD GNB1 along with several other seizure-associated genes such
89 as PRKCZ (chr1:2082566, p-value=1.8e-41, MAF=1.08%) and CDK11A (chr1:1645366, p-
90 value=6.25e-8, MAF=2.4%) were clustered within a one mega base window in the chromosome
91 1p36 region (**Figure 2a**). Of note, GNB1 has been shown to bind to growth hormone releasing
92 hormone receptor (GHRHR) and 5-hydroxytryptamine receptor 1B (HTR1B or serotonin receptor)
93 (**Figure 2b**). The 1p36 region is often used for karyotyping and diagnosing neurodevelopmental
94 disorders related to *1p36 deletion syndrome*^{13,14}. This fact further corroborates our results in
95 SANAD where for seizure-related phenotypes, we found numerous contiguous probes with MAF
96 >1% and significantly low p-values (e.g. NBPF1, **Supplementary table 3**).

97 In SANAD outside the chromosome 1p36 region we found several genes of interest including six
98 loci exceeding the p value threshold of < 1e-25 and MAF >=1% (**Figure 1**). Amongst these some
99 notable genes of interest included HEATR1, CNTNAP3 and GABRB3 (See discussion for further
100 details). In the independent analysis of the Australian cohort the top gene of interest for 12-month
101 remission to anti-epilepsy drugs was found within the PPFIA2 gene using CNV genotype

102 univariate analysis (chr12:82081470, p-value= 6.21e-06, MAF= 4.4%). PPFIA2 also replicated as
103 the top hit in the CNV genotype multivariate joint model with variable selection (chr12:82081470,
104 p-value=2.21e-06) (**Supplementary table 1b**). PPFIA2 belongs to the LAR protein-tyrosine
105 phosphatase-interacting protein (liprin) family¹⁵ and is known to be involved in pathways related
106 to Neurotransmitter release cycle and transmission across chemical synapses
107 (<https://pathcards.genecards.org/>). Previous studies¹⁶ have indicated that Ca²⁺ modulated liprin- α
108 proteins capture KIF1A-driven dense core vesicles (DCV) in dendritic spines¹⁶.

109 In the joint meta-analysis of SANAD and Australian cohort the top hit of interest was a locus
110 within the DAGLA gene (chr11:61462424, p-value=0.000301, MAF=1%). DAGLA is a neural
111 stem-cell derived dendrite regulator which is involved in 2-Arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG)
112 signaling in the central nervous system (CNS)¹⁷⁻¹⁹. It helps in axonal growth during neurogenesis
113 in early stages of development and in addition helps with neuroinflammatory response in the brain
114 (**Supplementary table 1c**). Other interesting results for meta-analysis included ASIC2 (Acid
115 Sensing Ion Channel Subunit 2) (chr17:31454867, p-value=8.54e-19) which was the top hit in
116 LRR multivariate models whereas GNB1 successfully replicated in the LRR univariate model
117 (chr1:1793111, meta p-value=9.49e-16).

118 Across all analyses and cohorts, the most distinct common CNV-phenotype signal with the highest
119 number of contiguous probes and significant p values was found within the WWOX gene
120 (MAF=47%, 48 contiguous probes for CNV genotypes and 66 contiguous probes in the LRR
121 analysis) (**Supplementary table 4**). This CNV was found to be exclusively associated with drug-
122 response phenotype in SANAD. Though WWOX is a known candidate gene for epilepsy and could
123 potentially have real seizure related effects in the brain²⁰⁻²², its association with the drug-response
124 was less convincing in the meta-analysis and in the Australian cohort. The fact that WWOX

125 harbors one of the most fragile sites in the human genome further puts these results in the grey
126 area for biological interpretation and warrants further experimental validation.

127

128 **CNV dosage effects in the UKBEC and NABEC cohorts**

129 Briefly, in the UKBEC study we generated two sets of CNVs calls from two different genotyping
130 platforms namely Illumina Omni 1M chip and a custom Immuno chip. Next we analysed these two
131 datasets independently with Illumina platform specific parameters in cnvHap²³ (See methods). In
132 the Omni 1M chip we detected 9,242 homozygous deletions (type 0), 1,29,929 heterozygous
133 deletions (type 1), 7,840 heterozygous duplications (type 3) and 546 homozygous duplications
134 (type 4). Genome-wide CNV breakpoint information for all cohorts is available in the
135 supplementary data section. Next for every probe in these two platforms we derived expected CNV
136 genotypes based on posterior probability from cnvHap and used these values for univariate and
137 multivariate association analyses using the multiphen²⁴ method with gene expression data from
138 different brain regions in the UKBEC study (see methods). In total in the UKBEC analysis we
139 generated 96 sets of transcriptome-wide CNV QTL results across CNV genotypes, LRR,
140 univariate and multivariate methods for eight brain regions. The top (rank 1) result for these
141 analyses is reported in **Supplementary table 1d, 1e**. The most notable observation in these results
142 is a cluster of significant CNV QTLs within one mega base pair window on chromosome 9 which
143 consistently harbored the top hit from different brain regions (**Figure 2a, Supplementary table**
144 **1d, 1e**). Two genes of interest from this cluster included TDRD7 (p-value < 1e-269, MAF=2.6%)
145 for CNV genotypes and NANS for LRR based models (p-value < 1e-269). N-acetyl-neuraminic
146 acid synthase or the NANS gene synthesises sialic acid in humans and has the highest
147 concentration in the brain. Biallelic recessive mutations in NANS are known to cause intellectual

148 disability with short stature²⁵ and plays an important function in neural transmission and
149 ganglioside structures in synaptogenesis²⁶. Interestingly in the UKBEC Immuno chip dataset the
150 top hit ANP32B (p-value < 1e-269, MAF=1.8%) was located within the same chromosome 9 gene
151 cluster containing TDRD7 and NANS. Here, ANP32B, like TDRD7 and NANS was consistently
152 the top hit in all brain regions (**Figure 2a, Supplementary table 1d, 1e**). ANP32B is known to
153 regulate gene expression²⁷ and leads to transcriptional repression of the KLF5 gene²⁸. Interestingly
154 NANS and ANP32B also lie near the GABBR2 gene. GABBR2, though not associated with any
155 of our epilepsy phenotypes or harbored any CNV with MAF >1% in any of the cohorts, is known
156 to cause Developmental and epileptic encephalopathy 59 (DEE59)²⁹ (malacards) and was further
157 shown to bind to GNB1 (**Figure 3b**).

158 In our analysis for UKBEC and NABEC datasets we discovered many additional significant loci
159 and regions of interest. One important example we highlight here is the significant cis CNV QTL
160 between serotonin and dopamine receptors on chromosome 11. In this instance we found probes
161 in the HTR3B gene to be significantly associated with DRD2 gene expression (e.g. CNV
162 genotypes at chr11:113802601 MAF=1.1% associated with DRD2 probe id 3391654 with p-
163 value=5.88e-81 in white matter brain region) and probes in the DRD2 gene was found to be
164 significantly associated with HTR3B gene expression (e.g. LRR in the DRD2 gene was associated
165 with HTR3B probe id 3349661 with p-value < 1e-308 using LRR joint model with variable
166 selection in cerebellum brain region) (**Figure 4**). Further delving into the serotonin biosynthesis
167 pathway we additionally discovered significant cis CNV QTL for CNVs in the cortisol receptor
168 gene CRHR2 which was associated with the expression of the nearby INMT gene (p-value < 1e-
169 20 in putamen and frontal cortex brain regions using LRR joint model with variable selection

170 method). INMT is known to N-methylate indoles such as tryptamine, which interacts with
171 tryptophan to produce serotonin (**Figure 4**).

172 So far, all analyses we have reported here are based on a overlapping moving window across the
173 genome i.e. CNV calling and association were performed for segments of the genome consisting
174 of both genic and intergenic regions. In addition to this, for the UKBEC Omni chip dataset, we
175 also performed CNV analysis on a gene-by-gene basis. The motivation for this approach is to find
176 CNVs lying within a gene and to further uncover its local effect on exonic expression. This
177 approach could potentially help identify relative importance of exons in a given tissue. To this end,
178 we called CNVs through the cnvHap HMM model but for all human genes individually (with a 5
179 kilo base pair window around gene boundary). Next, we derived expected CNV genotypes and
180 associated them with eight different UKBEC gene expression matrices using our univariate and
181 multivariate association models. Some example results for genes with common CNVs are as
182 follows. For the putamen brain region and in the HEATR1 gene the CNV-dosage analysis using
183 Multiphen joint model with variable selection identified exon 4 to be most significant (probe
184 id=2462530), for PRKCZ it was exon 10 (probe id=2316299) and for WWOX it was exon 5 (close
185 to the last exon, probe id=3700865) (**Supplementary figure 1**). A joint consensus analysis of
186 important exons identified through CNV genotypes, LRR, univariate and multivariate methods
187 remain to be explored. However, we have provided a complete set of results containing CNV-
188 dosage effects in all brain regions using different methods in the supplementary data section.

189 **NMF analysis if UKBEC Omni dataset**

190 Application of the Non-negative factorization method allowed us to deconvolute the UKBEC gene
191 expression dataset from 10 regions into meta exons or genes (also referred to as hidden genes or
192 patients in the literature). This transformation of gene expression data can be biologically

193 interpreted as exons and genes which are consistently over or under expressed in different regions
194 of the human brain (**Figure 5 a, b**). For the 1p36 region we ran the NMF algorithm on two
195 expression matrices. One is derived from averaging the expression values across 10 regions
196 (aveALL) and second is a combined expression matrix including all brain regions (Full set). On
197 analysing the relative frequency of individual exons in these results (NMF consensus clustering)
198 we discovered two gene clusters in the chromosome 1p36 region (**Figure 6, Supplementary table**
199 **5**). The first cluster was located around CDC42 gene with nearby genes (~1 mega base pair
200 window) such as RAP1GAP, USP48, HSPG2 and LUZP1. The second cluster was found around
201 CHD5 and included nearby genes KCNAB2, CAMTA1 and ACOT7. Further, application of NMF
202 for every gene individually (with 5 kilo base pairs window around gene boundary) allowed us to
203 see which exons are consistently over or under expressed across various brain regions. In
204 summary, first we applied the NMF deconvolution to the chromosome 1p36 region in the UKBEC
205 omni dataset with rank 10 and 20 for two expression matrices derived from all brain regions, and
206 then separately to all known human genes (rank 2 to 6, for 2 derived expression sets for ten brain
207 regions separately (see methods).

208

209 **Discussion**

210 Our results complement the recent large-scale studies in Epilepsy GWAS^{1,30} by filling the gap for
211 small and intermediate CNVs and its effect on seizures and drug response phenotypes. We found
212 that population level analysis of CNVs leverages more power to detect previous findings such as
213 GNB1 for neurodevelopmental disorders³¹ as well as uncovered new disease associated loci.
214 Existing protein structures depicting the interaction of GNB1 with HTR1B, and growth hormone-
215 releasing hormone (GHRHR) receptors further strengthens our CNV results in the SANAD cohort.

216 These observations also highlight the power of population aware methods for CNV genotyping³².
217 This is especially significant since unlike the cnvHap algorithm current methods for CNV
218 detection from bead array platforms usually apply hidden markov model (HMM) in a single
219 sample mode and fail to capture information which could be leveraged for modelling the dosage
220 landscape in the human genome³³. These aspects of our analyses along with univariate and
221 multivariate models distinguish our results from the current literature and further lead to new
222 findings. Some highlights of new genes we reported for Epilepsy phenotypes like seizure counts
223 and seizure frequency included PRKCZ, HEATR1 TRDN, CNTNAP3, AEBP2 and GABRB3.
224 PRKCZ is a calcium (Ca^{2+}) dependent gene known for memory function or long-term
225 potentiation^{34,35}. HEATR1 also known as BAP28 is required for pre-ribosomal RNA transcription
226 by RNA polymerase I and is known to cause brain abnormalities in zebrafish³⁶ and drosophila³⁷.
227 TRDN leads to muscle contraction by Ca^{2+} release and a known causal gene for *Cardiac*
228 *arrhythmia syndrome with or without skeletal muscle weakness* (CARDAR)³⁸⁻⁴¹ (malacards). The
229 relevance of CNTNAP3⁴²⁻⁴⁴ and GABRB3⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ for neurological diseases is well documented in
230 current literature (**Supplementary figure 2**). Lastly, the AEBP2 gene codes for a subunit in the
231 core Polycomb repressive complex 2 (PRC2)^{48,49} which affects histone H3K27 (H3K27me3)
232 trimethylation⁵⁰ on the chromatin leading to long term epigenetic silencing, also referred as cellular
233 memory. Based on these observations we suggest the possibility that these genes might lead to the
234 manifestations of secondary symptoms in Epilepsy or other neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g
235 memory loss or arrhythmia). These results also strongly indicate that transcriptional regulation and
236 heterogeneity is likely to be important for critical brain functions and homeostasis.
237 Our CNV results for UKBEC and NABEC cohorts complement the current SNP QTL results^{8,51,52}
238 in current literature. To the best of our knowledge our study is one of few which has elucidated

239 the dosage effect of small CNVs in different regions of the brain in a comprehensive manner.
240 Further our replication model based on LRR signals was consistent in uncovering meaningful
241 genes for neurology or the brain functions. For instance, in the case of the SCN1B gene, which is
242 a known candidate gene for Lennox-Gastaut syndrome, we did not detect any CNVs in all our
243 cohorts (which could be due to low probe density). However, by using the LRR based model in
244 the UKBEC dataset we uncovered suggestive signals in particular brain regions such as putamen,
245 white matter and occipital cortex (**Supplementary table 6**).

246 The convergence of top hits of CNV QTL in UKBEC Omni chip and Immuno chip data to the
247 chromosome 9 gene cluster which also happens to harbor the GABBR2 gene (G protein-coupled
248 receptor 3 family and GABA-B receptor subfamily) strengthens the clustering phenomenon earlier
249 reported in the original UKBEC SNP eQTL study. Further experiments aimed at better
250 understanding the causal mechanisms behind such clustering could potentially provide new
251 information related to human brain function and warrants further investigations. Importantly based
252 on our observations we suggest that *in-tandem* transcriptional regulation of collocated genes in the
253 genome could be an important mechanism by which important molecular functions are carried out
254 in the brain. To this end our NMF results from the UKBEC expression dataset hint that
255 transcriptional sense and relative position of exons (i.e. exons which are transcribed early along
256 the RNA polymerase machinery) might have higher or lower overall RNA concentration in the
257 cell (**Supplementary table 7**). This differential expression of exons which could potentially affect
258 splicing might be interpreted as *RNA amplitude* for a given exon in a tissue. The clustering of
259 CNV-phenotype signals in SANAD e.g. GNB1 region on chromosome 1p36 or the chromosome
260 9 CNV QTL cluster in UKBEC results provides suggestive evidence for the existence of such
261 phenomenon. However, the underlying mechanism for this remains to be elucidated and

262 experimentally validated. Lastly, the reciprocal CNV dosage effect we observed in the HTR3B
263 and DRD2 genes and its link to the CRHR2 - INMT metabolic pathway is potentially a new genetic
264 finding. This molecular axis possibly explains how the brain maintains homeostasis and balances
265 the critical role of neurotransmitters and hormones through the genomic regulation of serotonin,
266 dopamine and cortisol. Based on these findings and the results for GNB1 we conclude that CNVs
267 through its effect on protein receptor complexes has an important role to play in neurological
268 diseases and maintaining homeostasis in the brain.

269

270 **Methods**

271 **Cohorts**

272 **Epilepsy cohorts**

273 Similar to our previous study⁴, in our main CNV analysis in Epilepsy we adopted a prospective
274 cohort design instead of case-control designs. Our discovery cohort consisted of 916 subjects from
275 the Standard and New AED (SANAD) clinical trial and a secondary replication cohort consisted
276 of 380 subjects recruited from the royal Melbourne and Austin hospitals in Australia. A brief
277 description of all clinical variables analysed in these cohorts, including common phenotypes for
278 meta-analysis is described in the supplementary material. The main phenotype categories analysed
279 can be broadly divided into seizure related phenotypes (e.g. seizure frequency, total number of
280 seizures etc) and 12-month remission to AED medication (responders vs non-responders).
281 Epilepsy and seizure classification were based on the latest ILAE guidance. The main types of
282 Epilepsy in our study consisted of focal, generalized and unclassified Epilepsy. Genotyping of UK
283 and Australian samples was carried out using Illumina 660 bead chips at the Sanger Centre at
284 different points of time. Further quality control measures based on heterozygosity, sample call

285 rates and relatedness were carried out on the raw intensity data. Additional information on
286 genotyping and quality control for these cohorts can be found in our earlier reports⁴.

287

288 **The UKBEC and NABEC study**

289 The UKBEC study consists of 134 individuals of European descent who were confirmed to be
290 neuropathologically normal during life and had a median age of 59 years of age⁸. 74.5% of patients
291 are male and the most common cause of death in these individuals was heart attack. Further details
292 about tissue collection and genotyping have been reported in detail in earlier studies⁸. Briefly, the
293 whole transcriptome was available for 10 brain regions based on their relevance to human disease
294 and reported to exhibit high expression profiles. RNA was extracted from postmortem brain tissues
295 with randomization and checked for quality. Next, processed RNA was analysed through the
296 Affymetrix Exon 1.0 ST array. Next, all arrays were processed by robust multi-array average
297 normalisation and log 2 transformed in two different ways. Genomic DNA from samples from the
298 post-mortem brain tissue using Qiagen's DNeasy kit and subsequently genotyped on Illumina
299 Omni-Quad bead chip and a custom ImmunoChip designed to fine map autoimmune disorders.
300 GenomeStudio v.1.8.x was used for processing intensity data from which log R ratio (LRR) and
301 B allele frequency (BAF) was derived and exported for CNV analysis.

302 The NABEC study^{9,10} consists of approximately 360 individuals of European descent and free
303 from any neuropathological disorders. RNA was quality checked and extracted for hybridization
304 onto Human HT12v3 expression beadchips. Raw gene expression data was further transformed
305 using cubic spline and log transformed. Next, expression values were re-mapped using ReMOAT
306 onto human genome build 19 and annotated with genes with reliable data and free from common
307 polymorphisms. Genomic DNA for the NABEC study was extracted and genotyped on Illumina

308 Infinium HumanHap550 chips. Similar to the UKBEC study, intensity values LRR and BAF were
309 processed using genome studio software and exported for subsequent CNV analysis.

310

311 **CNV calling - two approaches - moving window and gene by gene approach**

312 Similar to our earlier studies^{32,33} we relied on the cnvHap algorithm²³ as the main CNV discovery
313 method. cnvHap is a multi-platform CNV-SNP haplotype based CNV detection algorithm which
314 uses Log-r ratio and B-allele frequency jointly to discover and genotype CNVs simultaneously.
315 cnvHap was shown to have more sensitivity in detecting smaller common CNVs with high
316 genotyping accuracy. Due to its population aware mode of model training, it was pragmatic to use
317 this method for CNV-phenotype association in large cohorts which were originally genotyped on
318 bead array chips for SNP GWAS or SNP eQTL studies. All cohorts analysed in our study including
319 for Epilepsy (UK and Australia), UKBEC and NABEC were genotyped on different versions of
320 Illumina bead array chips, hence were subjected to a common CNV pre-processing pipeline.
321 Briefly, for each cohort two intensity measurements, log-R ratio (LRR) and B-allele frequency
322 (BAF) were exported from Illumina genome studio software as final reports.

323 Next, the exported intensity measurements were normalised for GC content and further regressed
324 out from LRR values. Genomic wave effects were removed by fitting a localised loess function.

325 In the main cnvHap analysis, joint CNV-SNP haplotype structure information was incorporated to
326 refine CNV predictions and further based on allele frequencies, expected CNV genotypes were
327 calculated for subsequent association analysis. First, we fine-tuned our CNV analysis pipeline to
328 reproduce known common CNVs in our cohorts. We chose the WWOX intronic deletions as
329 reported by the gnomAD database in the region chr16:78371638-78385000 (Grch 37/hg19) which
330 has a deletion and a multi-CNV with allele frequency of 34% to 54% respectively

331 **(Supplementary figure 3, 4)**. Missense mutations in exons of WWOX have been reported to be
332 associated with highly pathogenic WOREE syndrome in epilepsy, which usually occurs in young
333 children and has a very poor prognosis. In SANAD we re-discovered this intronic CNV in WWOX
334 as common deletions with an allele frequency of 47% spanning the region chr16: 78373644 -
335 78384121. Manual inspection of cluster plots of LRR and BAF showed distinct homozygous
336 deletions spanning more than 40 contiguous probes which was the highest amongst all CNVs in
337 all our cohorts. This contiguity of probes was also reflected through significant association with
338 epilepsy drug response phenotype in the LRR based analysis of SANAD (without cnvHap calls).
339 However, we failed to detect similar common CNVs in WWOX in our Australian replication or in
340 the joint meta-analysis (multi-platform integration) of SANAD and Australian cohort through
341 cnvHap. Of note, our replication cohort from Australia had batch effects and around 30% of
342 samples were excluded from our CNV analysis pipeline. Unlike the SANAD cohort the resulting
343 sample size from Australia (N=280) thus had limited statistical power to detect and genotype
344 common CNVs on a broad allele frequency spectrum at genome wide significance level. However,
345 results from the Australian cohort independently and in the meta-analysis with SANAD were able
346 to replicate many of the primary findings and in addition were enriched for genes related to
347 neurological conditions, hence reported in our analysis. For meta-analysis of our Epilepsy and
348 Australian cohorts, we utilised the multi-platform integration feature of cnvHap, where intensity
349 values for each genotyping probes from the UK and Australian cohorts were modelled jointly in
350 the HMM model for CNV genotype predictions.

351 **Association models**

352 One of the main goals of SNP eQTL studies is enabling better understanding of GWAS loci. Here,
353 in our study design we aimed at emulating this approach by finding new CNV loci for Epilepsy

354 phenotypes in SANAD and Australian cohorts and then leveraging CNV eQTL analysis in normal
355 human brain regions from the UKBEC and NABEC studies for understanding CNV signals for
356 Epilepsy. The CNV eQTL results and gene NMF programs (described below) from the UKBEC
357 and NABEC cohorts can be used as an independent resource for replication and validation of a
358 priori disease hypothesis as well for other neurological diseases. Our association analysis for
359 Epilepsy cohorts, UKBEC and NABEC consisted of six different linear modes implemented in the
360 Multiphen software²⁴. These models were based on two approaches of CNVs detection 1)
361 Expected CNV genotypes derived from cvnHap and 2) Log-r ratio based raw intensity
362 measurements (i.e. without using cvnHap and for secondary validation of CNV-phenotype
363 signals). Next, two modes of CNV signals were analysed using 3 linear models: a) standard
364 univariate model (phenotype \sim CNV genotypes /LRR) b) Multiphen joint model (CNV
365 genotypes/LRR \sim Phenotypes) and c) Multiphen joint model with backward variable selection
366 (CNV genotypes/LRR \sim Phenotypes (subset)). Of note, in our analysis only the results of Cnv
367 association with epilepsy phenotypes in SANAD is considered to be the main discovery results
368 and all other reported results from Australia, UKBEC and NABEC are meant to be used as
369 replication results with a priori hypothesis. We used 5 LRR principal components and gender as
370 covariates for the SANAD cohort and only gender for the Australian, UKBEC and NABEC
371 studies. The main criteria for choosing parameters for cvnHap and covariates for Multiphen were
372 reproducing allele frequency of common CNVs e.g. matching WWOX deletion frequency from
373 gnomAD CNV results and reproducibility of known genes for neurological diseases.

374

375 **NMF gene programs**

376 Non-negative matrix factorization is a popular method in data science for deconvoluting complex
377 data including images and gene expression data. It has been successfully used for finding subtypes
378 of cancer and more recently for finding common gene programs across multiple single cell gene
379 expression data. Here, we have measurements for all human genes and their corresponding exons
380 in 10 brain tissues with an additional set derived from the average expression across all 10 brain
381 tissues. With the aim of finding common exons or genes which are consistently over expressed or
382 under expressed in these 11 sets of gene expression data matrices, we leveraged the NMF algorithm
383 to find meta exons/genes and corresponding meta patients. We performed this analysis using two
384 approaches. First, a gene-by-gene approach where for all 20, 000 human genes we extracted probes
385 within a 5-kbps window around each gene and derived 11 sets of brain tissue expression data.
386 Next, for these matrices we ran the NMF algorithm 50 times for rank 2 to 6. Next, from the output
387 of multiple NMF runs we extracted meta exons or genes using consensus clustering methods as
388 described here⁵³. Next, from these results we counted how many times each probe occurs in each
389 gene program for ranks 2 to 6. Here, frequency of these counts may be interpreted as relative
390 importance of exons which might have deeper biological or disease relevance. In the second
391 approach instead of a gene boundary we ran the NMF analysis over a genomic region e.g.
392 chromosome 1p36 region.

393

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399 and helping with data interpretation.

400

401 **Additional information**

402 Any additional information required to reanalyse the data reported in this paper is available from
403 the lead
404 contact upon request.

405

406 **Declaration of interests / Competing interests**

407 No external or financial interests to be declared.

408 **No organs and tissues were procured from prisoners.**

409 **Data and Code availability**

410 **Correspondence**

411 Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be
412 fulfilled by
413 the lead contact, Dr Tisham De (tisham.de08@imperial.ac.uk or de.tisham@gmail.com).

414

415 **Materials availability**

416 Samples and further materials related to the SANAD study and the Australian Epilepsy cohort can
417 be requested from the lead author or Dr Michael R Johnson, Department of Brain Sciences,
418 Imperial College London, UK.

419 Materials requests for the UKBEC and NABEC study should be addressed to the respective
420 authors of the original study.

421

422 **Data and code availability**

423

424 **Data**

425

426 UKBEC study data is available on Gene Expression Omnibus as described by the authors of the
427 original study. Microarray CEL files and processed data is under the accession number GSE46706.
428 SNP data is available through dbGAP. All data in our database are publicly available or open
429 source hence do not require any ethical guidelines.

430 All association results are available on Zenodo with url <https://zenodo.org/records/14946834>

431

432 **Code**

433 All codes used to process and analyse data are published, and the source code is currently available
434 at.

435 Multiphen: <https://github.com/lachlancoin/MultiPhen>

436 cnvHap: <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/people/l.coin>

437

438 This study did not generate new reagents or software code.

439

440 **Author contributions**

441 T.D., L.J.M.C. and M.R.J. were involved in study design, performed analysis, and wrote the
442 manuscript. L.J.M.C and M.R.J. advised and supervised the CNV, transcriptomics and multi
443 phenotype association aspects of this work. T.D conceived and performed the NMF analysis for
444 the UKBEC transcriptomics dataset. All authors contributed to the overall interpretation of results
445 and the discussion section of the manuscript.

446

447 **LEGENDS**

448 **Figure legends**

449 **Figure 1. Manhattan plot.** Figure depicting the CNVs associated with seizure phenotypes in the
450 SANAD cohort. Genes with p value < 1e-25 are highlighted and marked.

451

452 **Figure 2. a) GNB1 gene cluster.** Figure showing the ~ 1 megabase gene cluster in the
453 chromosome 1p36 region for CNVs significantly associated with seizure related phenotypes in
454 SANAD. Notable results included TTLL10, GNB1 and PRKCZ. **b) Protein structures of GNB1.**
455 Three-dimensional protein structures from the pdb database showing the protein complexes of
456 GNB1 bound to **i)** growth hormone receptor protein GHRHR and **ii)** serotonin receptor protein
457 HTR1B.

458

459 **Figure 3. CNV QTL results in the UKBEC study. a)** Figure highlights the ~ 1 megabase window
460 where the top (rank 1) hits from UKBEC analysis for ten brain regions were found to be clustered
461 (**Supplementary table 1 d,e**). Notable genes included TDRD7, ANP32B and NANS (GABBR2
462 also lies within this cluster and is a known epilepsy gene but was not found to be significant in our

463 results). **b)** Protein complex from the pdb database depicting the three-dimensional structure of
464 GNB1 bound to GABBR2.

465

466 **Figure 4. The genetic link between cortisol, serotonin and dopamine.** Top panel shows the cis
467 CNV QTL of cortisol receptor gene CRHR2 with INMT and its link to the tryptamine metabolite.
468 The bottom panel shows the reciprocal cis CNV QTL (or dosage) of DRD2 and HTR3B and its
469 link to the serotonin synthesis pathway.

470

471 **Figure 5. NMF analysis in the UKBEC study.** **a)** Summary of the brain regions analysed in the
472 UKBEC and NABEC studies. **b)** Overview of the NMF deconvolution analysis in the UKBEC
473 gene expression dataset.

474

475 **Figure 6. NMF gene clusters.** Overview of the two gene clusters uncovered through the NMF
476 analysis in the UKBEC gene expression dataset. Average all is derived by averaging gene
477 expression across the ten brain regions for every probe id whereas Full set refers to the combined
478 gene expression matrix from all brain regions.

479

480 **Supplementary figure 1. CNV-QTL in Putamen.** Figure showing the association of CNV genotypes
481 with exon level gene expression in three genes of interest namely HEATR1, PRKCZ and WWOX for
482 the putamen brain region in the UKBEC dataset. The model of association used was Multiphen
483 joint model with variable selection for all panels except log-r-ratio result for WWOX (*). In this
484 case the model was Multiphen joint model only. This analysis was done on a gene-by-gene basis
485 (see methods).

486

487 **Supplementary figure 2. GABRB3 interaction with GNB1.** Reactome pathway details showing
488 GABA B receptors interacting with G protein alpha-I, 0 beta and gamma subunits which leads
489 to the activation of GIRK (KIR3) potassium channels.

490

491 **Supplementary figure 3. CNVs in WWOX.** Figure shows the CNVs in the WWOX gene from the
492 gnomAD database (GRCh37 / hg19).

493

494 **Supplementary figure 4. CNVs in WWOX.** Figure shows the CNVs in the WWOX gene from the
495 gnomAD database (GRCh38 / hg38).

496

497

498

499 **Supplementary tables**

500 **Supplementary table 1. Top results from all analyses.** Table showing the top rank 1 results for
501 SANAD, Australian cohort, Meta-analysis, UKBEC and NABEC studies.

502

503 **Supplementary table 2. Clinvar database results for GNB1.** CNV and SNP annotations for the
504 GNB1 gene in the clinvar database.

505

506 **Supplementary table 3. Association results in SANAD for chromosome 1p36.** Association
507 results for seizure phenotypes in SANAD in the chromosome 1p36 region.

508

509 **Supplementary table 4. Association results for the WWOX gene.** Association results for the
510 drug-response phenotype in SANAD for CNV genotypes and LRR using univariate and
511 multivariate models.

512

513 **Supplementary table 5. NMF results for chromosome 1p36 in UKBEC.** Frequency of exons in
514 different gene programs uncovered through the NMF analysis of UKBEC dataset for NMF ranks
515 10 and 20 for gene expression matrices a) average all and b) full set.

516

517 **Supplementary table 6. LRR results for SCN1B.** Results for association of Log R Ratio with
518 gene expression in different regions of the brain from the UKBEC dataset. Only three brain regions
519 had p values < 1e-03 namely putnam, white matter and occipital cortex.

520

521 **Supplementary table 7. Transcriptional sense of nearby genes.** Table showing the
522 transcriptional sense and the NMF analysis (rank 2 to 6) of genes located close to each other in the
523 genome. Top exon refers to the most frequent exon in the NMF gene programs. NMF analysis was
524 done for every gene separately with a 5 kilo base window around the gene boundary (see methods).

525

526

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